

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHENOMENON OF PATRIOTISM IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the phenomenon of youth patriotism in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan, the priority tasks of education of patriotism in young people in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan are studied. Also, the need to study the processes of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan and the factors that develop it is analyzed.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, scientific-methodological basis, socio-philosophical, phenomenon, spiritual growth, patriotism, modernity, historical-philosophical basis, objectivity, historicity, systematicity, analysis, synthesis, induction-deduction.

INTRODUCTION. At a time when serious threats to humanity are increasing, it is becoming an urgent social task for scientists to educate people to feel patriotism, to teach them to fully understand the meaning of the concept of "Motherland", to explain that patriotism is a high moral principle. However, moral principles are also specific forms of moral awareness, in which moral requirements are highlighted in a relatively general way. They are manifested in the form of demands placed on the individual by the society, and determine the moral essence of a person, the meaning of his life, and the main aspects of his interactions with people. As a result, principles serve as the basis for many moral standards, indicating the general direction of human behavior.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The processes of spiritual growth in Uzbekistan are promoted on the basis of the principle of "From national revival to national growth", conceptual ideas in the works, speeches, articles and selective meetings of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as well as the philosophical heritage of the East and the West. serves as a scientific-methodological basis for this research.

A number of studies have been carried out that include the problems related to clarifying the importance of the processes of spiritual growth in the new stage of development of Uzbekistan. S. Shermuhammedov, A. Saidov, B. Toraev, J. Yakhshilikov, N. Joraev, Q. Nazarov, S. Otamurodov, S. Karimov, A. Kholbekov, R. Jumaev, B. Karimov T. Our scientists, such as Joraev, I. Ergashev, S. Joraev, M. Kyrgyzboev, A. Erkaev, M. Bekmurodov, V. Kochkarov, M. Jakbarov, A.

Muminov, have conducted various researches on the development of the social sphere in society. carried out. Scientists such as R. Ubaidullaeva, Kh. Abdusattorova have conducted research on the importance of the innovative factor in the new era of social development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. According to ethicist Abdulla Sher, "patriotism is a moral concept that means a person's love for his Motherland, his desire to preserve it. ... Feel joy from the successes achieved by the Motherland on all fronts, sadness from the failures, be proud of the Motherland, look with love at every inch of its land, every brick of its buildings, ancient monuments, achievements in science and art, protecting them like the apple of an eye, all this is patriotism." According to another scientist, Erkin Yusupov, "love for the country is not a political ideology, but a perfect morality and mature spirituality. Accordingly, all qualities included in the concept of patriotism are included in the system of moral values. Therefore, patriotism in its essence is deeper than simple respect for a region, a country. Patriotism is the attitude to the homeland that rises to the level of spirituality and gives purpose and direction to human activity. "Patriotism can be seen in the activities of some individuals." However, such activity becomes an important factor of development only when it is socialized and rises to the level of spirituality characteristic of the majority.

Another scientist, Qiyamiddin Nazarov, interprets patriotism as a universal concept and connects it with the features of the idea of development of the Motherland. In his opinion, "patriotism is a socio-spiritual feeling that emerged in the process of historical development, formed under the influence of the external environment and times, and matured. It is formed, expanded and improved throughout the life of each person. Of course, when a person grows up and becomes an adult, he realizes that the whole Earth is a common space for a human child, he learns that Mother Earth is the only Homeland for man in the Solar System. He understands the need to protect this land. Patriotism based on such a vision is a universal concept. So, patriotism is a worldview based on the appreciation of belonging, formed on the basis of the qualities of social consciousness.

It should be noted that patriotism is used in foreign scientific sources as patriotism (Greek: patriotes - countryman, "patris" - Motherland) as love for the Motherland, attachment to the country of birth and loyalty to it. However, patriotism is often interpreted as a spiritual and ideological weapon against the enemies of the Motherland, the basis of the national identity of the people, and love for the history, culture, and values of the Motherland. In fact, compared to

patriotism, the scope of patriotism is much wider in terms of content - it is a relatively specific form of humanitarianism. It is not only a struggle to protect the freedom of one's countrymen, but also actions in the way of human freedom. In this sense, the defense of the Motherland is the defense of a person, the defense of the nation. But this protection, as we said above, can be manifested not only on the battlefield, but also in all areas. In this sense, patriotism, in addition to glorifying the homeland, is the ability to protect its dignity and independence. The importance of patriotism is more evident in the most responsible periods of the country's development. In this sense, patriotism is a mature spirituality.

Research scientist E. Kalkanov interprets patriotism as a social phenomenon. According to his opinion, "patriotism as an attributive feature of forms of social consciousness, the etymological meanings of the concepts of "Motherland" and "patriotism" - the meaning of loving the motherland and one's people - are given as a human feeling - a spiritual phenomenon. Also, patriotism means that a person feels closeness to certain peoples and territories, self-awareness and the formation of loyalty to the motherland and people, and loyalty is the root of them, and loyalty is a condition for the existence of patriotism. For example, he analyzes the fact that patriotism and internationalism are two opposing sides of loyalty to the motherland and people in the human heart, which differ from each other and require each other. gives the following definition: "Patriotism is the ethnogenetic, natural-legal, moral, economic and political feelings of faith that arise in the psyche of people in a certain geographical area, within a certain community - people, nation. It belongs to the attributive features of a number of forms of social consciousness and acts as a coordination of certain beliefs and behavior. "Patriotism is a spiritual phenomenon with its own substantial integrity." So, patriotism opens with the concepts of selflessness and loyalty. Their manifestation shows patriotism in a person.

Another important issue related to the moral content of the concept of patriotism is its aspects related to moral norms such as national pride and honor. In educational and methodological literature on social sciences, patriotism is interpreted as one of the respectable values ingrained in the blood of our people. Also, patriotic education is an integral part of the national ideology, and it is very important to educate military personnel in this spirit. Because one of the tasks of the national independence ideology is "... to realize identity in the thinking of our compatriots, to be faithful to historical memory, to

preserve our sacred values, to perfect patriotic feelings." So, in fact, patriotic education is carried out on the basis of ideological educational programs, and patriotism is inculcated based on the ideology of the development of society.

Based on the above-mentioned opinions, the following conclusion can be made by summarizing the conceptual views on the philosophical, moral, social and spiritual nature of patriotism:

First of all, patriotism is an important source of internal mobilization of the state's vitality for the development of society, a moral basis that manifests itself as an individual's active civic views, his readiness to selflessly serve his homeland.

Secondly, patriotism is serving the country with loyalty, ensuring the integrity and sovereignty of the country, its national security, sustainable development, the priority of the interests of society and the state over individual interests and aspirations, as the highest goal of life, manifested in the activities of the individual, all social groups and layers of society. The main criterion for dividing duty and obligation is social behavior and self-revealing virtue.

Thirdly, patriotism is not a limitation of social and individual freedoms of citizens in relation to the state, but rather an incentive and a condition for the comprehensive development of civil society, consciously and voluntarily accepted views.

Loyalty to the motherland is one of the highest principles of morality, these principles are not created by any individual, they are considered to be legal rules that have arisen as forms of moral consciousness in the course of life in accordance with certain social relations. legal provisions that reflect the general requirements related to the spiritual essence, duty, meaning of life and the nature of interactions between people, indicate the general direction of human activity and serve as a basis for certain norms of behavior it is said.

It is correct to bring devotion as a concept compatible with loyalty to the country. In the explanatory dictionary, "Sacrifice is the behavior of people who are ready to sacrifice their legitimate interests, even their lives, for the benefit of others, who can pass themselves off as the highest goals and ideals common to society. a spiritual concept expressing actions" is defined. In general, the qualities present in the human heart are mutually harmonious and serve to improve the perfection of the person.

Devotion is often cited in artistic and popular literature. In particular, according to O. Makhmudov in his work "Farzandnoma", "the first sign of devotion is patriotism. This great human quality is in the nature of a devotee.

Where there is patriotism, loyalty to the Motherland and the idea of protecting it like the apple of one's eye becomes the highest goal. Strong faith in a noble goal, trust in fellow countrymen, purity of speech, courage and selflessness in taking responsibility constitute the content of his life. Naturally, people in this category are called devotees." So, as can be seen from these thoughts, it is possible to see that the qualities of patriotism and self-sacrifice are very close to each other.

According to some researchers, a comprehensive approach to patriotic education requires a goal-oriented and multifaceted approach. It is analyzed that patriotism should serve as the main goal of all activities aimed at educating a perfect person and the beginning of educational work. It is also shown that the strong sense of patriotism and national pride in young people ensures the strength and stability of their needs for spiritual maturity. Also, "patriotic education is a planned, systematic, goal-oriented and coordinated activity of state bodies, public associations and organizations on the formation of a high sense of patriotism, a sense of loyalty to one's country, preparation for fulfilling civic duty and protecting its interests in young people" , in scientific generalizations, new views about the social content, scientific necessity and theoretical importance of patriotism are put forward. However, patriotism can be interpreted more broadly from the point of view of educational subjects.

CONCLUSION. In the current era, patriotism is required to become a characteristic characteristic of young people who deeply respect the history and fate of the motherland, people, and are able to show examples of selflessness in the interests of the Motherland. Because, only when love for the motherland and trust in its future are formed on the basis of a single goal aimed at the interests of the nation, patriotism becomes a virtue of all people who connect their fate with the fate of the homeland and the nation.

References:

1. Abdullah Sher. Ethics - Tashkent: National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan, 2010. -B.143.
2. Абрамова Г.С. Психология только для студентов: Учебное пособие для вузов. – Москва.: ПЕР СЭ, 2001. – С.168
3. Камбаров А.М. Актуальные проблемы духовно–нравственного и патриотического воспитания молодежи на современном этапе // Проблемыдуховно–нравственного и патриотического воспитания военнослужащих и пути решения. - Ташкент: ABC РУ. 2001. - С. 5.
4. Кулакова Л. И., Западов В.А. А.Н.Радищев: Путешествие из Петербурга в Москву /Комментарий. –Ленинград, Белогор, 1974. –С.116.

5. Kurbanov R. Yu. The role of the national idea in educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. Autoref: dis ... fals.fan.nom. -Tashkent: 2008. -B. 10-13
6. The idea of national independence: basic concepts and principles. - Tashkent: New Age Generation, 2004. -B.123.
7. Spirituality: an explanatory dictionary of basic concepts. - T.: Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, 2010. - B.333.
8. Mamatov H.T. Legal culture and problems of formation of civil society in Uzbekistan. Tashkent. 2009. -B. 202.
9. Маслова В.А. Введение в когнитивную лингвистику. – М., 2008. – С. 46
10. Nazarov Q. Philosophy of ideas. Practical guide. -Tashkent: Academy, 2011. -B.84.
11. Kalkanov E.T. Laws of dependence of the formation and implementation of patriotism (social-philosophical analysis). Fals.fan.nom dis. autoref. - Tashkent: UzMU, 2011. -B. 18.
12. Юсупов Э. Инсон камолотининг маънавий асослари. -Тошкент: Университет, 1998. -Б. 148-164.

